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Social Footprint Disclosures And Investors' Confidence Of Listed Industrial Goods Companies In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The neglect of host communities by companies who derive their economic resources from these social environment has made investors to lose confidence on the activities of these companies. The main objective of this study was to examine the effect of social footprint disclosures on investors' confidence of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria. The research design adopted for the study was ex post facto, secondary data were used and the population of the study consisted of 13 listed industrial goods companies out of which a sample size of 11 was purposively selected. The data used were analyzed using ordinary least square regression analysis and the statistical package employed was E views version 13. The analysis revealed that indigenous staff employment disclosure has a significant positive effect (Coef. = 0.18; p -value = 0.001) on earnings multiple; indigenous venture disclosure has a significant positive effect (Coef. = 0.10; P -value = 0.002) on earnings multiple; social donations disclosure has a significant positive effect ((Coef. = 0.14; P -value = 0.032) on earnings multiple of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria. Thus, it was concluded that social footprint disclosure is one of the indices that affect investors' confidence. It was therefore, recommended that the management of listed industrial goods companies should adopt comprehensive and transparent reporting on their indigenous staff employment practices by including data on indigenous representation across various levels of the organization, details on recruitment and retention strategies aimed at indigenous welfare development.

Keywords:

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Globally, there have been a drive for circular economy and this has made companies to engage in Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) practices more than before. Among these, the "Social" component, often referred to as the social footprint or social sustainability has gained significant prominence. According to Eshiett et al. (2023), a company's social footprint encompasses its impact on people – including employees, customers, communities, and the broader society – through its operations, products, and services. Historically, investors primarily focused on financial performance indicators to assess a company's health and future prospects. However, a growing body of evidence suggests that companies with strong social performance and transparent social disclosures tend to be more resilient, sustainable, and ultimately, more valuable in the long run (Eshiett et al., 2023). This recognition has led to

an evolution in investor behavior, with a heightened emphasis on non-financial information. Investors are increasingly seeking to understand not only what a company does but also how it does it, particularly regarding its social impact.

Social footprint disclosures involve the systematic and transparent reporting of a company's social performance. This can include information on employee relations (diversity, fair labor practices, health and safety), customer relations (product safety, customer satisfaction, complaint handling), community engagement (local employment, philanthropic activities, impact on host communities), and human rights in the supply chain. The underlying premise is that such disclosures provide valuable insights into a company's risk management, ethical standards, operational efficiency, and its ability to maintain a social license to operate (Abasiofon et al., 2024). Among the social footprints of companies are the employment of indigenous staff, indigenous venture supports and social or philanthropic disclosures. Indigenous staff employment disclosure refers to the practice of organizations publicly reporting on the number, representation, and initiatives related to the employment of Indigenous peoples within their workforce. Indigenous venture support entails offering both monetary and non-monetary support to native company owners and entrepreneurs. This assistance can come in a number of forms, such as loans, grants, training, mentorship, and access to markets and networks (Haalboom, 2022). Social donations disclosure refers to the public reporting of monetary or in-kind contributions made by individuals, corporations, or foundations to charitable organizations, non-profits, or other philanthropic causes. Highlighting philanthropic activities can enhance a company's public image, attract socially conscious consumers and employees, and build goodwill.

Investor confidence refers to the level of optimism and trust that investors have about the performance of financial markets, specific companies, and the broader economy. It reflects their willingness to engage in investment activities, such as buying stocks, bonds, or real estate, based on their expectations of future economic conditions and potential returns. Investors feel confident when they perceive a favorable balance between the potential returns they can earn and the risks involved in their investments (Ali, 2022). Disclosure of social footprint is strategic to the sustainability of any firm especially industrial goods companies that are the engine room of sustainable development to any developing economy like Nigerian. But many companies do not show commitment to the negative impact of their business activities on the society by giving back to them through employment of indigenes, supports to social entrepreneur, social and philanthropic donation and community development. This according to them may not add up to their financial bottom lines. Yet prior studies have establish that disclosure of corporate social responsibility by firms could improve the reputation of such firms, enhance competitive advantage and thus reduce information asymmetry by signally to investors that they are not exposed to dangers (risk) of hostility from both the society and the environment (Jerry, et al., 2022; Eshiett et al., 2023).

The empirical literature were reviewed and some gaps were identified and the major among them was the fact most of the previous studies examined the effect of social footprint or social sustainability disclosures on other performance measures other than investors' confidence such as financial performance for instance financial performance (Megawati & Pratama, 2024; Nallo et al. 2024), cost of capital, (Ime et al., 2024; Akpan & James, 2024; Abasiofon et al., 2024)) and market value. It was also found that most of the studies focused on other sectors of the economy other than industrial goods companies (Dattijo et al. 2024; Ali, 2022). Unfortunately there was no unanimous findings because of numerous divergent findings. Thus, it was as a result of the identified gaps that this study was undertaken to ascertain the effect of social footprint disclosures on investors confidence of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria.

2.0 Literature review and hypotheses development

Social footprint disclosure

Social footprint refers to the impact an organization has on people and communities. It's a key component of sustainability, often alongside economic and environmental impacts. Social footprint disclosures refer to the practice of organizations publicly reporting on their social impacts and performance (Eshiett et al.,

2023). The organizational social footprint focuses on a broader, more systemic impact on human well-being and community development, often tied to sustainability goals. Guiso et al. (2022) states that social footprint, or social sustainability, includes everything that affects the relationship between a company and its stakeholders. “from how much and how reliably suppliers pay, to how the product affects lives, and from the treatment of small farmers to the effect of alcohol on health and communities” These disclosures go beyond financial statements and often include information about, labor practices and decent work, employee wages and benefits, working conditions, health, and safety employee rights, impacts on local communities, indigenous peoples, and vulnerable groups, investments in local communities and Customer well being. Social footprint disclosures are important as it shows transparency and accountability for companies’ social impacts, both positive and negative (Eshiett et al., 2023). Transparency allows stakeholders (investors, consumers, employees, regulators, civil society) to assess a company's commitment to social responsibility. By disclosing social risks, companies can identify and mitigate potential negative impacts that could lead to legal issues, reputational damage, or operational disruptions. Companies that increase their social footprint know the value of their relationships with people, communities, and society.

Investor’s confidence

Investor confidence refers to the level of optimism and trust that investors have about the performance of financial markets, specific companies, and the broader economy. It reflects their willingness to engage in investment activities, such as buying stocks, bonds, or real estate, based on their expectations of future economic conditions and potential returns. Investors’ confidence is defined as the investors’ willingness to engage in the investment opportunities and associated intermediation channels available to them based on their perception of risk and return (Guiso et al., 2022). Investors feel confident when they perceive a favorable balance between the potential returns they can earn and the risks involved in their investments. A sense of assurance in the mechanisms and regulations designed to protect them from potential losses or fraudulent activities within the financial marketplace is crucial. High investor confidence translates into a greater willingness to commit capital to businesses and projects. Investor confidence is the willingness of current and potential investors to engage in investing in the company or in other intermediation channels available between them and the firm (Robson & Akpan, 2024). The Price-to-Earnings (P/E) ratio is a widely used financial metric that helps investors assess the value of a company's stock. It's calculated by dividing the current market price per share of a company's stock by its earnings per share (EPS). Earnings multiple serves as a measure of investor confidence because it encapsulates expectations for future earnings, perceptions of risk, comparative valuation within an industry, market sentiment, investor perception of management and strategy, considerations of long-term investment horizon, and the broader economic and market environment (Ozioko & Onah, 2022).

Indigenous staff employment disclosures and earnings multiplier

Indigenous staff employment disclosure refers to the extent to which companies report their efforts in hiring, training, promoting, and retaining local or native employees in the communities where they operate. This disclosure forms part of social sustainability or social footprint reporting, highlighting a firm’s commitment to local development, inclusivity, and equitable employment practices. According to signaling theory, firms disclose non-financial information (like indigenous employment initiatives) to signal their ethical and socially responsible behavior to the market (Khaveh et al., 2025). Transparent reporting about employing indigenous staff signals stability, inclusiveness, and reduced social risk, are attributes that improve a firm’s image and long-term sustainability prospects. By disclosing indigenous staff employment practices, firms demonstrate commitment to social equity and local empowerment, which enhances trust and investor confidence. This can translate into higher valuation multiples as investors perceive the firm as socially responsible and less exposed to reputational or operational risks. Empirical studies have found that social responsibility disclosures, particularly those related to employee relations and local community engagement, positively affect investors’ perception and firm valuation. Khaveh et al. (2025) found that disclosure of information about community indigene development enhances shareholders wealth. Umar and Atiku (2025). revealed that community development

expenditure has significant effect on net profit margin of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria respectively. Eshiett et al. (2023) found that community disclosure significantly improves firm's value; Meiryani et al. (2023) found that transparent environmental and social disclosures improve investor trust and are associated with higher firm value as measured by valuation multiples. Olorunnisola and Usman (2023) reported that social sustainability disclosures, including indigenous employment and local hiring initiatives, significantly enhance investors' confidence in Nigerian firms, measured through higher earnings multiples. Ogunleye et al. (2023) also observed that human capital and social responsibility disclosures improve corporate reputation and investor trust, leading to a positive market response. Ayon and Oyedokun (2022) unveiled that community involvement displayed a positive yet statistically insignificant effect on Return on Asset (ROA). Based on the foregoing, it was hypothesized;

Ho₁: Indigenous staff employment disclosures does not have any significant effect on earnings multiple of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria.

Indigenous venture support disclosures and earnings multiplier

Indigenous venture support disclosure refers to the public reporting by organizations on their efforts and contributions to support the development, growth, and sustainability of businesses owned and operated by Indigenous peoples. According to Godefroit-Winkel et al., (2022), indigenous venture support is a crucial aspect of corporate social responsibility (CSR). This entails offering both monetary and non-monetary support to native company owners and entrepreneurs. According to Akpan and James (2024), investors who see verifiable indigenous venture support disclosure can update expectations about future cash flows and firm risk, increasing willingness to pay higher multiples. Bariweni (2024) posited that if investors interpret indigenous venture support disclosure as evidence of such investments, multiples may rise to reflect higher expected long-term earnings. Conversely, if indigenous venture support disclosure corresponds to costly programs with immediate earnings dilution (or is judged as managerial rent-seeking), investors may penalize the firm, lowering multiples.

Studies of ESG and sustainability disclosures in emerging markets find that credible social foot print, often produces positive valuation effects, especially where disclosures reduce political or operational risk. Kornom-gbaraba et al. (2025) revealed that community development cost disclosure is positive insignificant effect on financial performance at 5% level of significance. Akpan and James (2024) found that community responsibility disclosures has no significant effect on weighted average cost of capital. Oladele and Tedekon (2024) concluded that that investments in community development (CD), corporate donations and charity (CDC), and stakeholder engagement (SE) positively impact financial performance. Ubokudom et al (2024) found that indigenous venture support disclosures have significant negative effect on the cost of equity of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. Ime et al. (2024) found that indigenous venture supports and staff welfare disclosures have significant negative effect on weighted average cost of capital of listed pharmaceutical firms in Nigeria. Bariweni (2024) found a significant negative relationship between community development activities and the return on equity. Thus, this study hypothesized that;

Ho₂: Indigenous venture support disclosures does not have any significant effect on earnings multiple of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria.

Social donations disclosures and earnings multiplier

Social or philanthropic donation disclosure refers to a company's voluntary reporting of charitable giving, community development spending, or other social donation activities in its annual or sustainability reports. Iloma and Chukwu (2023) noted that social donations disclosures send a positive signal about the firm's ethical orientation, reputation, and long-term commitment to social responsibility. This signal reduces uncertainty and attracts socially responsible investors, thereby increasing investor confidence and the firm's earnings multiple. By disclosing philanthropic activities, firms demonstrate responsiveness to community and societal stakeholders. According to Oladele and Tedekon (2024), many corporate managers admit that well managed donations not only boost company image in the eyes of customers but also could be a competitive advantage. They further opine that "companies that make substantial

donations are likely to promote a socially responsible public image, which could extend to other aspects of business practice, such as high standards of product quality and customer care. Oladele and Tedekon (2024) concluded that that investments in community development (CD), corporate donations and charity (CDC), and stakeholder engagement (SE) positively impact financial performance. Dattijo et al. (2024) found that firms engaging in strategic philanthropy enjoy improved financial performance and positive investor responses. Adepiti (2023) noted that philanthropic donations have a positive and statistically significant influence on firm value. Adebayo & Olayinka (2021) found that community and philanthropic disclosures positively influence the earnings per share and market capitalization of Nigerian manufacturing firms, implying higher investor confidence and valuation multiples. Iloma and Chukwu (2023) found that while philanthropic donations improve social image, their disclosure did not significantly influence share price. Based on the above findings, it was hypothesized that;

Ho₃: Social donations disclosures does not have any significant effect on earnings multiple of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria.

2.2 Theoretical framework

Signalling theory by Spence (1973)

This study is anchored on Signalling Theory as propounded by Michael Spence (1973). The theory originates from information economics and addresses the problem of information asymmetry between two parties, typically one possessing superior information and the other operating with limited knowledge. As noted by Connelly et al. (2011), corporate managers possess private information regarding the firm's operational strength, risk exposure, sustainability orientation, and long-term strategic positioning. Investors, on the other hand, rely largely on publicly disclosed information to evaluate firm quality and make investment decisions. This imbalance creates uncertainty, which may weaken investor confidence and distort market valuation. Signalling theory posits that informed parties can reduce information asymmetry by transmitting credible signals to uninformed parties (Dattijo et al., 2024). According to Emuebie et al. (2021), for a signal to be effective, it must be observable, costly to imitate, and capable of distinguishing high-quality firms from low-quality ones. This theory supports this study because, comprehensive and transparent social footprint reporting serves as a credible signal of responsible management and effective risk mitigation. By voluntarily disclosing socially responsible activities and sustainability commitments, management communicates confidence in the firm's governance structures, operational resilience, and compliance culture.

2.3 Empirical reviews

Khavesh et al. (2025) examined the impact of environmental and social performance disclosures on shareholders wealth of Malaysian companies. The research design adopted for the study was ex post factor and secondary data were used. The population of the study was made up of all listed companies on the Malaysian Exchange with 45 companies purposively selected as the sample size of the study. The results of the study revealed that disclosure of information about community indigene development enhances shareholders wealth. Gad (2024) examined the impact of social disclosures on the financial performance of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. The findings from the regression results reveals positive significant impact on the Return on Assets (ROA) of the social disclosures of oil and gas companies in Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study recommends that; right and appropriate policies that will enhance the social disclosure should be put in place by the Environmental Management Sectors of Nigeria.

Akpan and James (2024) examined the relationship between corporate social responsibility and weighted average cost of capital of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. Secondary data was extracted from the annual report of the company under study and was analyzed using panel data. The findings of this study revealed that philanthropic responsibility disclosure has a significant negative effect on weighted average cost of capital; Community responsibility disclosures has no significant effect on weighted average cost of capital and environmental responsibility disclosure has a non-statistically significant effect on the weighted average cost of capital of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

Abasiofon et al. (2024) examined the effect of corporate social responsibility disclosures on the cost of equity of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. The findings of this study revealed that customer disclosures have a significant positive effect on the cost of equity; environmental responsibility disclosures have a positive but not statistically significant effect on the cost of equity while indigenous venture support disclosures have a significant negative effect on the cost of equity of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Ime et al. (2024) examined the effect of corporate social responsibility disclosures on cost of capital of pharmaceutical firms listed on the floor of Nigeria Exchange Group from 2013 to 2022. The findings of this study revealed that environmental responsibility disclosures have an insignificant but positive effect on weighted average cost of capital while indigenous venture supports and staff welfare disclosures have significant negative effect on weighted average cost of capital of listed pharmaceutical firms in Nigeria.

Eshiett et al. (2023) examined the disclosure of social footprint on firms' value in Nigeria. Findings indicate that community disclosure significantly improves; employee relation disclosure insignificantly decreases the firm value of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria; customer complaints disclosure significantly improves the firm value of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Adepiti (2023) examined the impact of social sustainability disclosure on firm value of listed financial services firms in Nigeria. The findings of the study indicate that workforce gender diversity (female workforce) disclosures and social donation disclosure as indicators of social sustainability disclosure, have a positive and statistically significant influence on firm value. On the other hand, health and safety disclosure has a positive but insignificant effect. The study concluded that enhancing firms' social sustainability disclosure, particularly in relation to workforce gender diversity and education sponsorship, have the potential to enhance the firms' value.

3.0 METHODS

The research design adopted for this study was ex post facto because data used were historical. The population of this study consisted of all industrial goods companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group from 2015 to 2024. According to the Nigerian Exchange group Factbook (2024), there are 13 listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria. The sample size of this study was 11 (eleven) industrial good firms purposively selected. The data for social footprint disclosures were derived using content analysis. Checklist was developed based on Global Reporting Initiatives disclosure guidelines and theoretical developments by previous researchers. The disclosure checklist consisted of 15 disclosure items and these were indigenous employment disclosures - 5 items, indigenous venture support disclosures - 5 items and social donation disclosures - 5 items. Each reporting item on the checklist was assigned a value of '1' if disclosed and '0' if the item is assumed relevant but not disclosed. The score or disclosure index for each disclosure parameter was the ratio of aggregate actual disclosure to the expected disclosure. This is given thus;

The disclosure index = $\frac{\text{Aggregate actual disclosure score}}{\text{Total Expected disclosure}} \times 100$

Model specification

The model used in this study was adapted from the one specified by Eshiett et al. (2023) which was modified to fit this study as given below;

Investors confidence = f(Social footprint disclosures)

Earnings multiple = f(Indigenous employment disclosures, indigenous venture disclosures, philanthropic donation disclosures)

$$EMPL_{it} = B_0 + b_1 INED_{it} + b_2 IVSD_{it} + b_3 SODD_{it} + e_{it} \quad (4)$$

Where;

EMPL = earnings multiple

INED = indigenous employment disclosure

IVSD = indigenous venture disclosure

SODD = Social donation disclosures

bo	=	Constant
b ₁ - b ₄	=	Slope coefficient to be determined in the study
<i>e</i>	=	Stochastic disturbance
i	=	i th firm
t	=	time period

Table 3.1: Operationalization of the variables

S/N	Variables	Measurements	Source
Dependent Variable			
1	Earnings multiple	Ratio of MPS to EPS	<i>Udosen and Akpan (2024)</i>
Independent Variables			
2	Indigenous staff employment disclosure	Dummy variables that proxy disclosure of employment of indigenous staff in annual financial statements with "1" and "0" for otherwise	Abasiofon <i>et al.</i> (2024)
3	Indigenous venture support Disclosure	Dummy variables that proxy disclosure of indigenous venture support information in annual reports with "1" and "0" for otherwise	Gad (2024)
4.	Social donation disclosure	Dummy variables that proxy disclosure of Social Donation information in annual reports with "1" and "0" for otherwise.	Abasiofon <i>et al.</i> (2024)

Source: Author's Compilation (2026)

4.0 ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

4.2.1 Descriptive analysis

Table 4.1.1 Descriptive statistics of the effect of social footprint disclosures on investors' confidence

	EMPL	INED	IVSD	SODD
Mean	4.481114	0.438143	0.402714	0.702857
Median	6.451199	0.440000	0.500000	0.300000
Maximum	9.750273	1.000000	0.860000	1.000000
Minimum	2.1155.20	0.600000	0.340000	0.400000
Std. Dev.	10.98771	0.507587	0.196557	0.245965
Skewness	-9.327353	0.067964	-0.143338	0.247907
Kurtosis	120.7278	1.495620	1.853915	1.769677
Jarque-Bera	106558.8	6.654772	4.070773	5.131949
Probability	0.000000	0.035887	0.130630	0.076844
Sum	626.6006	30.67000	30.29000	24.70000
Sum Sq. Dev.	2.167108	6.528059	2.665784	4.174429
Observations	110	110	110	110

Source: Author's computation (2026)

Table 4.1 represents the results obtained from the descriptive statistics of the study. For earnings multiple, on average, firms in the industrial goods sector had 4.48 times their earnings per share (EPS), the

minimum however, was 2.11 time, highest was 9.75 times and standard deviation was 10.988 times. These show that the earnings multiple in the sector was high as of the study period and that investors would pay premium for companies' current earnings. In the case of the independent variables, table 4.1 shows that the mean of indigenous staff employment disclosure (INED) was 0.44 and a standard deviation of 0.51. This implies that on the average, the selected industrial goods companies made about 44% percent disclosures of their indigenous staff employments. Similarly, the result shows that the mean of indigenous venture support disclosure (IVSP) was 0.40 with a standard deviation of 0.65. This implies that about 40% of the indigenous venture supports were disclosed. Finally, social donation disclosure has an average value of 0.7 implying that these companies made about 70% of their social donation activities.

4.1.2 Correlation analysis

Table 4.2: Correlation analysis of the relationship between social footprint disclosures and investors' confidence

	EMPL	INED	INVD	SODD
EMPL	1.0000			
INEP	0.1456	1.0000		
IVSD	0.2034	0.4568	1.0000	
SODD	0.3422	0.4521	0.5085	1.0000

Author's computation (2026)

In the case of the correlation between social footprint disclosures and investors' confidence table 4.2 shows that there is a positive association (0.17) between earnings multiple (EMPL) and indigenous employment disclosures (INED). It is also observed that there is a positive association between indigenous venture support disclosures (IVSD) (0.20) and earnings multiple. Table 4.1 also shows that there is a positive and moderate association (0.34) between earnings multiple and social donation disclosure (SODD).

4.3. Regression analysis

The researcher employed the OLS regression analysis to analyze the cause-effect relationships between the dependent and independent variables and the summary of the regression analysis is as given in table 4.1.3

Table 4.3: Summary of regression result of the effect of social footprint disclosures on investors' confidence

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	2.216812	0.371860	5.261415	0.0001
INEP	0.1777305	0.021957	5.392648	0.0001
IVSD	0.1035843	0.465280	5.251815	0.0002
SODD	0.1363299	0.281047	4.482926	0.0320
Effects Specification				
			S.D.	Rho
Cross-section random			0.554434	0.6727
Idiosyncratic random			0.386726	0.3273
Weighted Statistics				
R-squared	0.21554	Mean dependent var		0.266063
Adjusted R-squared	0.181481	S.D. dependent var		0.403888
S.E. of regression	0.386793	Sum squared resid		26.03187
F-statistic	42.54214	Durbin-Watson stat		1.724560
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000134			
Unweighted Statistics				
R-squared	0.2526	Mean dependent var		1.235227
Sum squared resid	77.28773	Durbin-Watson stat		0.580862

Source: Authors computation (2026)

From table 4.3, it is observed that the R-squared of the OLS regression (0.2526) indicates that about 25% of the systematic variations in investors' confidence as measured by earnings multiple in the pooled industrial goods firms over the period of interest was accounted for by the independent variable in the model. This implies that social footprint disclosures account for about 25% variation in investors' confidence of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The unexplained part (75%) can be attributed to the exclusion of other independent variables that could impact on investors' confidence but were however, captured in the error term. The F-statistic value of 42.5 and its associated P-value of 0.000 shows that the OLS regression model on the overall is statistically significant at 1% level, this means that the regression model is valid and can be used for statistical inference.

4.2 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Indigenous staff employment disclosures and earnings multiple

The result obtained from the OLS regression analysis in table 4.3 shows that indigenous staff employment disclosures has a significant positive effect (Coef. = 0.18; P -value = 0.001) on earnings multiple of listed industrial goods firms during the period under the study. This implies that a unit increase in indigenous venture disclosure would improve earnings multiple by 18%. The significant positive effect of indigenous staff employment disclosures on the earnings multiple highlights the growing recognition among investors of the value of diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) initiatives, particularly those focused on indigenous populations. This finding suggests that companies transparently reporting their efforts to employ indigenous staff are viewed more favorably by the market. This increased investor confidence can be attributed to several factors. Firstly, a diverse workforce, including indigenous representation, often brings a wider range of perspectives, experiences, and skills, leading to enhanced innovation, problem-solving, and adaptability within the company. This can translate into better business outcomes and competitive advantage. Secondly, such disclosures demonstrate a company's commitment to social justice and community integration, which can bolster its reputation and social license to operate, especially in regions with significant indigenous communities. This reduces potential social and political risks. Thirdly, employing indigenous staff can improve a company's understanding of and access to indigenous markets and communities, potentially opening up new business opportunities or fostering stronger relationships. Finally, investors may see indigenous staff employment as a sign of a progressive and forward-thinking management team, capable of navigating complex social landscapes and building a resilient organization, thereby warranting a higher earnings multiple. The findings of this study aligns with the work of Khaveh et al. (2025) who noted that disclosure of information about community indigene development enhances shareholders wealth. Also Emuebie et al. (2021) found a positive significant relation between social disclosures and earnings pers share

Indigenous venture support disclosures and earnings multiple

The result obtained from the OLS regression analysis in table 4.3 shows that indigenous venture disclosure has a significant positive effect ((Coef. = 0.10; P -value = 0.002) on earnings multiple of listed industrial goods firms during the period under the study. This implies that a unit increase in indigenous venture support disclosures would improve earnings multiple by 10%. The significant positive effect of indigenous venture support disclosures on the earnings multiple suggests that investors perceive such corporate actions as value-enhancing. This finding indicates that when companies publicly communicate their involvement in or support for indigenous ventures (e.g., through partnerships, investments, or capacity building), it fosters greater investor confidence. This confidence likely stems from several factors. Firstly, supporting indigenous ventures can be seen as a strategic move towards long-term sustainability and social license to operate. In many regions, particularly those rich in natural resources or with significant indigenous populations, strong relationships and positive community engagement are crucial for business continuity and risk mitigation. Investors may view these disclosures as evidence of a company's commitment to responsible business practices, reducing potential future conflicts or regulatory hurdles. Secondly, such support can enhance a company's reputation and brand image. A positive public perception, often associated with social responsibility, can attract a broader base of ethical investors and

potentially lead to increased customer loyalty and market share. Finally, indigenous ventures often tap into unique knowledge, resources, or markets, and by supporting them, companies might be seen as diversifying their portfolio or gaining access to untapped opportunities, leading to improved future earnings prospects. Investors, therefore, translate this perceived value and reduced risk into a willingness to pay a higher multiple for the company's earnings. The findings of this study negate the work of Abasiofon et al. (2024) and Ime et al. (2024) who found that indigenous venture support disclosures have a significant negative effect on the cost of equity of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Social donations disclosures and earnings multiple

The result obtained from the OLS regression analysis in table 4.3 shows that Social donations disclosures has a significant positive effect ((Coef. = 0.14; P -value = 0.032) on earnings multiple of listed industrial goods companies in Nigeria. This implies that a unit increase in social donation disclosures would improve earnings multiple of listed industrial goods companies by 14%. The significant positive effect of philanthropic donation disclosures on the earnings multiple underscores the increasing importance of corporate social responsibility (CSR) in investment decision-making. This finding suggests that transparency in a company's charitable activities positively influences investor confidence. One key reason is that philanthropic donations, when disclosed, signal a company's commitment to societal well-being beyond mere profit generation. This can enhance the company's reputation and moral standing, attracting investors who prioritize ethical considerations or view CSR as a proxy for good management. Good management, often associated with a long-term vision and stakeholder-oriented approach, is highly valued by investors. Furthermore, engaging in philanthropy can improve employee morale and attraction, leading to a more productive workforce and reduced turnover, which ultimately contributes to better financial performance. Investors may also infer that companies that engage in philanthropy are financially stable enough to allocate resources beyond core business operations, suggesting robust underlying profitability. The act of giving can also serve as a form of "insurance" against negative public sentiment or reputational damage, thereby reducing perceived risks for investors. Ultimately, investors view these disclosures as evidence of a responsible and well-governed entity, justifying a higher earnings multiple. The findings of this study align with the work of Adepiti (2023) who found that social donation disclosure as indicators of social sustainability disclosure, have a positive and statistically significant influence on firm value.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, the findings consistently demonstrate that specific indigenous-related social disclosures, specifically, indigenous venture support, philanthropic donations, and indigenous staff employment, exert a significant positive influence on a company's earnings multiple, serving as a robust indicator of enhanced investor confidence. This collective evidence suggests that investors are increasingly integrating social and ethical considerations into their valuation processes. Companies that transparently engage in and disclose their commitment to indigenous community development, broader philanthropy, and inclusive employment practices are perceived as more sustainable, reputable, and forward-thinking. This perception translates into a willingness among investors to assign a higher valuation to their earnings, reflecting a belief in the companies' long-term value creation, reduced risk profiles, and improved social license to operate. Therefore, the management of listed industrial goods companies should adopt comprehensive and transparent reporting on their indigenous staff employment practices by including data on indigenous representation across various levels of the organization, details on recruitment and retention strategies aimed at indigenous talent, career development programs, and initiatives to foster an inclusive workplace culture. Also, these companies should proactively and transparently disclose their engagement in and support for indigenous ventures. This should include detailed information on partnerships, investments, capacity-building programs, and any mutual benefits derived from these collaborations.

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